

Maximum Power Point Tracking by ANN Controller for a Standalone Photovoltaic System

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Abstract : In this paper, ANN controller for maximum power point tracking of photovoltaic (PV) systems is proposed and PV modeling is discussed. Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) methods are used to maximize the PV array output power by tracking continuously the maximum power point. ANN controller with hill-climbing algorithm offers fast and accurate converging to the maximum operating point during steady-state and varying weather conditions compared to conventional hill-climbing. The proposed algorithm gives a good maximum power operation of the PV system. Simulation results obtained are presented and compared with the conventional hill-climbing algorithm. Simulation results show the effectiveness of the proposed technique.

Keywords : Artificial neural network (ANN), hill-climbing, maximum power-point tracking (MPPT), photovoltaic.

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